

Social Debt in Agile Software Development Environments: A Systematic Literature Review

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Repository Overview

This repository provides a collection of documents offering insight into the process followed for conducting the systematic literature review on social debt. The repository is organized by topic, and each section contains documents related to specific phases of the process, as outlined below:

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2. Research Methodology

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4.3.1. Table 1: Sociotechnical factors Affected by Social Debt.

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